

Reconsidering Mesenchymal Stem Cell Therapy: From Cellular Identity to Mechanism-Oriented Translation

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Highlights

- The therapeutic efficacy of mesenchymal stem cells is not an intrinsic cell property, but a context-dependent outcome governed by manufacturing, delivery, and host immune state.

Abstract

The persistent inconsistency of mesenchymal stem cell clinical outcomes reflects a fundamental mismatch between biological mechanism, manufacturing variability, and trial design rather than a failure of the cells themselves.

Keywords: Mesenchymal stem cells; translational inconsistency; mechanism of action; paracrine signaling; extracellular vesicles; clinical trial design

Introduction

We read with great interest the recently published articles discussing the therapeutic applications of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). Over the past two decades, MSCs have been extensively investigated for their immunomodulatory and regenerative properties, leading to a rapid expansion of preclinical studies and clinical trials across a wide spectrum of diseases[1-4]. Nevertheless, despite the initial enthusiasm, clinical outcomes remain inconsistent and, in many indications, disappointing.

One critical issue lies in the biological heterogeneity of MSCs. MSCs derived from different tissue sources, donors, and culture conditions exhibit substantial variability in phenotype, secretory profiles, and functional potency[2, 5]. Although the minimal criteria proposed by the International Society for Cell Therapy provide a useful framework for defining MSC identity, these criteria are insufficient to predict therapeutic efficacy. As a result, MSCs classified under the same definition may represent functionally distinct cell populations with divergent clinical behavior.

Equally important is the growing recognition that the therapeutic effects of MSCs are largely mediated by paracrine and immunological mechanisms rather than long-term engraftment or differentiation[6]. Accumulating evidence suggests that short-lived MSCs, apoptotic MSCs, or even MSC-derived extracellular vesicles (EVs) can reproduce many of the observed therapeutic benefits. This paradigm challenges the traditional view of MSCs as “living drugs” and calls for a shift toward mechanism-driven rather than cell-centric therapeutic strategies. Furthermore, limitations in clinical trial design have contributed to the translational gap[7, 8]. Many trials rely on heterogeneous patient populations, poorly

defined endpoints, and insufficient consideration of disease stage or immune microenvironment. Without appropriate patient stratification and biologically relevant outcome measures, even well-characterized MSC products may fail to demonstrate efficacy in late-phase trials[9]. In light of these challenges, we believe the field would benefit from a strategic recalibration. Future research should prioritize (i) functional potency assays linked to defined mechanisms of action, (ii) standardized manufacturing and release criteria beyond surface marker expression, and (iii) rational clinical trial designs that align MSC biology with disease pathophysiology. In parallel, cell-free approaches such as MSC-derived EVs merit serious consideration as more controllable and scalable therapeutic modalities.

In conclusion, MSC-based therapy remains a promising but evolving field. Progress will depend not on increasing the number of trials, but on deepening our mechanistic understanding and aligning biological insight with translational strategy. We commend the journal for fostering discussion on this topic and hope these perspectives will contribute to ongoing efforts to refine and advance MSC-based therapeutics.

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Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

The authors declare that they have used generative AI and/or AI-assisted technologies in the writing process before submission, but only to improve the language and readability of their paper.

Credit author statement

Emre Kaya: Conceptualization; Writing - original draft; Visualization. **Selim Arslan:** Writing - review & editing; Critical revision of the manuscript; Validation.

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